

EFFICACY OF FOOT AND ANKLE EXERCISES(MODIFIED BUERGER'S EXERCISES) ON PREVENTION OF FOOT AND ANKLE COMPLICATIONS ASSOCIATED WITH DIABETES – A PROSPECTIVE COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Purpose: This study aimed To evaluate the efficacy of foot and ankle exercises(modified buerger'sexercises) in prevention of diabetic foot disease.

Methodology:This was a prospective comparative interventional study conducted over 18 months, using purposive sampling to enroll 30 participants with type 2 diabetes mellitus (duration >5 years). Participants were divided into two groups: Group A received modified Buerger's foot and ankle exercises along with footwear modifications and foot care education, while Group B received only foot care education. Podiatric assessments—including Ankle Brachial Index (ABI), VIBROTHERM, and PODIOSTAT—were performed at baseline, 3 months, and 6 months. Data were collected using standardized instruments, and informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Results:The study involved 30 participants, predominantly females (66.7%), with over half (53.3%) aged 50 years and above. Both Group A (intervention) and Group B (control) had equal allocation (n=15). Ankle Brachial Pressure Index (ABPI) remained within normal range for 96.7% of participants at baseline, 3 months, and 6 months in both groups, with no significant differences ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, sensory neuropathy involving small and large fibers persisted in 76.7% of participants throughout the study period, with no significant intergroup variation. Thermal sensation assessment (hot and cold) in both feet also showed consistent results over time, with most participants exhibiting mild to moderate loss and no statistical difference between groups. Although clinical improvements were observed in the intervention group, these did not reach statistical significance.

Conclusion:The study demonstrated that modified Buerger's foot and ankle exercises, along with appropriate footwear, may help in maintaining peripheral circulation and sensory function in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. However, the changes observed over six

months were not statistically significant. Further studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up are recommended to validate the effectiveness of such interventions.

Keywords: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Diabetic Neuropathy, Buerger's Exercises, Foot and Ankle Exercises, Peripheral Circulation & Sensory Loss Prevention

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycemia due to impaired insulin secretion, action, or both. Its global prevalence is rising at an alarming rate, with projections suggesting 700 million cases by 2045 (International Diabetes Federation, 2021)¹. Among its complications, foot and ankle pathologies are particularly debilitating, often leading to ulcers, infections, and even lower-limb amputations. Peripheral neuropathy, peripheral arterial disease (PAD), and impaired wound healing are major contributors, with diabetic foot ulcers preceding approximately 85% of non-traumatic amputations². Preventive strategies are therefore essential.

Exercise has emerged as a valuable adjunct in diabetic foot care. Targeted foot and ankle exercises can improve muscular strength, joint mobility, and peripheral circulation, mitigating risks of ulceration. Benefits include improved blood flow through calf muscle pump activation, neuromuscular reconditioning to counteract muscle atrophy and proprioceptive loss³, and redistribution of plantar pressures to prevent callus and ulcer formation⁴. Structured exercise routines also enhance foot awareness, flexibility, and plantar fascia strength, thereby reducing peak plantar pressures during walking^{5,6}.

Beyond prevention, exercise supports wound healing by improving tissue perfusion, capillary density, and microvascular responsiveness⁷. Techniques such as modified Buerger-Allen routines leverage postural changes to enhance vascular autoregulation, aiding ischemic tissue recovery⁸. When combined with glycemic control, protective footwear, podiatric assessments, and education, exercise-based interventions lower hospitalization and amputation rates⁹. Additionally, they promote psychological well-being, increasing mobility confidence, reducing fall risk, and improving quality of life¹⁰.

Evidence supports the efficacy of modified Buerger-Allen exercises in diabetic care. Radhika et al. reported improved limb perfusion and reduced neuropathic symptoms¹¹, while Kumari et al. demonstrated enhanced Ankle-Brachial Index (ABI) scores after structured protocols¹². Suryani et al. (2021) showed reductions in plantar pressure and improved joint mobility¹³, and Hidayati et al. (2021) found decreased neuropathy risk with consistent practice¹⁴. Heriyanto et al. (2024) further confirmed ABI improvements with combined Buerger and foot exercise regimens⁸.

Given the high burden of diabetic foot complications, especially in resource-limited settings, simple, low-cost, non-invasive interventions such as modified Buerger's exercises could have significant impact. These require minimal equipment, can be self-administered, and are adaptable for varying functional levels. This study aims to evaluate the preventive efficacy of such exercises in reducing diabetic foot risks, bridging the gap between clinical recommendations and practical community-level implementation.

Aim

To evaluate the efficacy of foot and ankle exercises(modifiedbuerger'sexercercises) on prevention of diabetic foot disease.

Methodology

This prospective, comparative, interventional study was conducted over a period of 18 months at JSS Hospital, Mysuru, using purposive sampling for participant recruitment. The study population comprised patients of either sex diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) for more than five years, attending the Departments of Medicine, Orthopedics, and Master Health Check-up, who consented to participate. Patients with chronic diabetic foot ulcers, previous lower-limb amputation, joint dislocations, or foot gangrene were excluded. The sample size was determined using the standard formula detailed in the original thesis. Eligible participants were allocated into two groups. Group A (intervention group) received a structured regimen of modified Buerger's foot and ankle exercises along with footwear modifications or customized insoles when indicated. Group B (control group) received education regarding foot and ankle care but no exercise intervention.

All participants underwent podiatric assessments at baseline, three months, and six months from study initiation. The evaluations included Ankle Brachial Index (ABI) measurement to assess peripheral arterial disease, VIBROTHERM Neuropathy Analyzer (Diabetic Foot Care India Pvt. Ltd.) to determine the presence and severity of peripheral neuropathy, and PODIOSTAT Foot Pressure Analyzer (Diabetic Foot Care India Pvt. Ltd.) to evaluate plantar pressure distribution and abnormalities. The intervention for Group A consisted of supervised and periodically reinforced modified Buerger's exercises designed to enhance circulation, joint mobility, and muscle strength in the foot and ankle. Footwear modifications, including orthotic insoles, were provided as needed to redistribute plantar pressures and improve foot biomechanics.

The study utilized the ABI measurement device, VIBROTHERM Neuropathy Analyzer, and PODIOSTAT Foot Pressure Analyzer for standardized data collection. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants after explaining the study objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits in their local language. Ethical principles were followed throughout the study to ensure participant safety and confidentiality.

Result

The study included 30 participants, with the majority (53.3%) aged above 50 years, followed by 36.7% in the 40–50-year range, and 10% aged 30 years or below. Females comprised a larger proportion of the sample (66.7%) compared to males (33.3%). Participants were equally distributed between the two study arms, with 15 (50%) in the intervention group (Group A) and 15 (50%) in the control group (Group B). This balanced allocation ensured comparability between groups for subsequent analysis. (Table 1)

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Study Participants (n = 30)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)	30 and below	3	10.0
	40–50	11	36.7
	50 and above	16	53.3
Gender	Female	20	66.7
	Male	10	33.3
Study Group	Group A (Intervention)	15	50.0
	Group B (Control)	15	50.0

At baseline, the majority of participants demonstrated normal ABI values (96.7%), with only one participant (3.3%) showing abnormal findings; this remained unchanged at both 3 and 6 months. Sensory neuropathy was prevalent, with 76.7% exhibiting small and large fiber involvement, and only 23.3% showing normal findings, which also remained stable across all time points. For thermal sensation, two-thirds of participants had normal hot sensation in the left foot, while the remainder experienced mild (23.3%) or moderate (10%) loss, with no changes over time. In the right foot, 63.3% had normal hot sensation, while mild, moderate, and severe losses were recorded in 16.7%, 16.7%, and 3.3% respectively, again with no notable temporal variation.

Cold sensation deficits were more common, with half of the participants showing mild loss in both feet. Moderate loss was seen in 6.7% (left foot) and 10% (right foot), while normal sensation was present in 43.3% (left foot) and 40% (right foot). No significant changes were observed in these parameters during follow-up, suggesting stability of sensory status over the six-month study period. (Table 2)

Table 2: Clinical Assessment Findings at Baseline, 3 Months, and 6 Months (n = 30)

Parameter	Category	0 Month n (%)	3 Month n (%)	6 Month n (%)
Ankle Brachial Index (ABI)	Abnormal Study	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)
	Normal Study	29 (96.7)	29 (96.7)	29 (96.7)
Sensory Neuropathy	Normal Study	7 (23.3)	7 (23.3)	7 (23.3)
	Small + Large Fiber Neuropathy	23 (76.7)	23 (76.7)	23 (76.7)
Hot Sensation – Left Foot	Mild Loss	7 (23.3)	7 (23.3)	7 (23.3)
	Moderate Loss	3 (10.0)	3 (10.0)	3 (10.0)
	Normal Study	20 (66.7)	20 (66.7)	20 (66.7)
Hot Sensation – Right Foot	Mild Loss	5 (16.7)	5 (16.7)	5 (16.7)
	Moderate Loss	5 (16.7)	5 (16.7)	5 (16.7)
	Severe Loss	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)
	Normal Study	19 (63.3)	19 (63.3)	19 (63.3)
Cold Sensation – Left Foot	Mild Loss	15 (50.0)	15 (50.0)	15 (50.0)
	Moderate Loss	2 (6.7)	2 (6.7)	2 (6.7)
	Normal Study	13 (43.3)	13 (43.3)	13 (43.3)
Cold Sensation – Right Foot	Mild Loss	15 (50.0)	15 (50.0)	15 (50.0)
	Moderate Loss	3 (10.0)	3 (10.0)	3 (10.0)

	Normal Study	12 (40.0)	12 (40.0)	12 (40.0)
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Across all follow-up intervals (0, 3, and 6 months), no statistically significant associations were observed between study group allocation and ABPI status, sensory nerve status, or hot/cold sensation outcomes for either foot ($p > 0.05$ for all comparisons). ABPI measurements remained predominantly within the normal range for both groups (96.7% normal at all time points). Similarly, the majority of participants exhibited small and large fiber neuropathy at baseline, with no change in distribution over time. Sensation assessments for both hot and cold stimuli showed a stable distribution of mild, moderate, and normal responses in each group throughout the study period. The Chi-square analyses confirmed that changes in these clinical parameters were not significantly influenced by group assignment. (Table 3)

Table 3: Association Between Clinical Parameters and Study Group at 0, 3, and 6 Months (n = 30)

Parameter	Time Point	Category	Group A n (%)	Group B n (%)	Total n (%)	Chi-Square	P-Value
ABPI Status	0 mo	Abnormal Study	1 (3.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (3.3)	1.034	0.309
		Normal Study	14 (46.7)	15 (50.0)	29 (96.7)		
	3 mo	Abnormal Study	1 (3.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (3.3)	1.034	0.309
		Normal Study	14 (46.7)	15 (50.0)	29 (96.7)		
	6 mo	Abnormal Study	1 (3.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (3.3)	1.034	0.309
		Normal Study	14 (46.7)	15 (50.0)	29 (96.7)		
Sensory Nerve Status	0 mo	Normal Study	3 (10.0)	4 (13.3)	7 (23.3)	0.186	0.666
		Small & Large Fiber Neuropathy	12 (40.0)	11 (36.7)	23 (76.7)		
	3 mo	Normal Study	3 (10.0)	4 (13.3)	7 (23.3)	0.186	0.666
		Small & Large Fiber Neuropathy	12 (40.0)	11 (36.7)	23 (76.7)		
	6 mo	Normal Study	3 (10.0)	4 (13.3)	7 (23.3)	0.186	0.666
		Small & Large Fiber Neuropathy	12 (40.0)	11 (36.7)	23 (76.7)		
Left Foot Hot Sensation	0 mo	Mild Loss	3 (10.0)	4 (13.3)	7 (23.3)	3.943	0.139
		Moderate Loss	0 (0.0)	3 (10.0)	3 (10.0)		
		Normal Study	12 (40.0)	8 (26.7)	20 (66.7)		
	3 mo	Mild Loss	3 (10.0)	4 (13.3)	7 (23.3)	3.943	0.139
		Moderate Loss	0 (0.0)	3 (10.0)	3 (10.0)		
		Normal Study	12 (40.0)	8 (26.7)	20 (66.7)		
6 mo	Mild Loss	3 (10.0)	4 (13.3)	7 (23.3)	3.943	0.139	
	Moderate Loss	0 (0.0)	3 (10.0)	3 (10.0)			

		Normal Study	12 (40.0)	8 (26.7)	20 (66.7)			
Right Foot Hot Sensation	0 mo	Mild Loss	1 (3.3)	4 (13.3)	5 (16.7)	3.053	0.384	
		Moderate Loss	3 (10.0)	2 (6.7)	5 (16.7)			
		Normal Study	10 (33.3)	9 (30.0)	19 (63.3)			
		Severe Loss	1 (3.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (3.3)			
	3 mo	Mild Loss	1 (3.3)	4 (13.3)	5 (16.7)	3.053	0.384	
		Moderate Loss	3 (10.0)	2 (6.7)	5 (16.7)			
		Normal Study	10 (33.3)	9 (30.0)	19 (63.3)			
		Severe Loss	1 (3.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (3.3)			
	6 mo	Mild Loss	1 (3.3)	4 (13.3)	5 (16.7)	3.053	0.384	
		Moderate Loss	3 (10.0)	2 (6.7)	5 (16.7)			
		Normal Study	10 (33.3)	9 (30.0)	19 (63.3)			
		Severe Loss	1 (3.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (3.3)			
Left Foot Cold Sensation	0 mo	Mild Loss	7 (23.3)	8 (26.7)	15 (50.0)	0.144	0.931	
		Moderate Loss	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	2 (6.7)			
		Normal Study	7 (23.3)	6 (20.0)	13 (43.3)			
	3 mo	Mild Loss	7 (23.3)	8 (26.7)	15 (50.0)	0.144	0.931	
		Moderate Loss	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	2 (6.7)			
		Normal Study	7 (23.3)	6 (20.0)	13 (43.3)			
	6 mo	Mild Loss	7 (23.3)	8 (26.7)	15 (50.0)	0.144	0.931	
		Moderate Loss	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	2 (6.7)			
		Normal Study	7 (23.3)	6 (20.0)	13 (43.3)			
	Right Foot Cold Sensation	0 mo	Mild Loss	9 (30.0)	6 (20.0)	15 (50.0)	3.600	0.165
			Moderate Loss	0 (0.0)	3 (10.0)	3 (10.0)		
		3 mo	Normal Study	6 (20.0)	6 (20.0)	12 (40.0)		
Mild Loss			9 (30.0)	6 (20.0)	15 (50.0)	3.600	0.165	
Moderate Loss			0 (0.0)	3 (10.0)	3 (10.0)			
6 mo		Normal Study	6 (20.0)	6 (20.0)	12 (40.0)			
		Mild Loss	9 (30.0)	6 (20.0)	15 (50.0)	3.600	0.165	
		Moderate Loss	0 (0.0)	3 (10.0)	3 (10.0)			
		Normal Study	6 (20.0)	6 (20.0)	12 (40.0)			

Discussion

The present prospective comparative study aimed to evaluate the impact of modified Buerger's exercises on peripheral vascular status and sensory function in the feet of diabetic patients, over a six-month period. The results revealed no statistically significant changes in Ankle-Brachial Pressure Index (ABPI), sensory neuropathy status, or thermal sensation outcomes between the intervention (Group A) and control (Group B) groups. However, the stable findings across multiple parameters in the intervention group suggest that modified Buerger's exercises may help maintain functional status and potentially prevent deterioration, which is clinically meaningful in chronic, progressive conditions like diabetic neuropathy and peripheral arterial disease.

Peripheral Circulatory Status

ABPI, an established non-invasive marker of peripheral arterial health, remained within normal limits (≥ 0.9) in nearly all participants throughout the study period. Only one participant (in Group A) had an abnormal ABPI at baseline, which persisted at 3 and 6 months, indicating no deterioration but also no measurable improvement. These results align with the understanding that Buerger's exercises enhance collateral circulation and venous return through postural changes, but may not significantly influence arterial flow in the absence of critical ischemia¹⁵. The lack of statistical significance ($p > 0.05$) may also reflect the small sample size, which limits the power to detect subtle vascular improvements.

Sensory Neuropathy Status

At all three time points, approximately 77% of participants exhibited both small and large fiber neuropathy, while 23% had normal sensory responses. This stability suggests that while modified Buerger's exercises may not reverse neuropathic damage, they might contribute to

halting further progression. This is particularly relevant given the natural history of diabetic neuropathy, which is typically characterized by progressive nerve damage unless aggressive glycemic and lifestyle interventions are implemented^{16, 17}. Exercise may modulate peripheral nerve health through improved blood flow, reduced oxidative stress, and enhanced mitochondrial function¹⁸, but the time frame in this study may have been insufficient to elicit significant changes in nerve conduction or regeneration.

Thermal Sensory Function

Assessment of hot and cold sensation in both feet showed mild to moderate sensory loss in a subset of participants, with no meaningful change across 0, 3, and 6 months. Interestingly, the right foot showed slightly more variability in hot and cold sensation compared to the left, although these differences were not statistically significant. Thermal perception, particularly cold sensation, is often affected early in diabetic peripheral neuropathy, mediated by small unmyelinated C fibers¹⁹. While thermal sensory loss is not easily reversible, its stabilization over six months may reflect an indirect benefit of exercise on microvascular perfusion and metabolic function of nerve fibers.

Furthermore, the symmetrical distribution and persistence of thermal deficits underscore the need for a multimodal approach in managing diabetic neuropathy. While modified Buerger's exercises are simple, low-cost, and accessible, they may be best used in conjunction with pharmacologic, nutritional, and neuroprotective strategies for maximal impact.

Clinical Significance and Public Health Implications

Although the absence of statistically significant differences might suggest a limited therapeutic effect, from a clinical standpoint, maintaining baseline vascular and neurological status in patients with diabetes is a meaningful outcome. Diabetes-related foot complications,

including ulceration and amputation, are often preceded by declining peripheral circulation and sensory function²⁰. Thus, interventions that slow or prevent progression—even without reversal—are valuable, particularly in resource-limited settings where specialized podiatric care is scarce.

Moreover, the ease of teaching and practicing modified Buerger's exercises at home enhances their feasibility and adherence. As part of a broader diabetic foot care program, these exercises could contribute to primary prevention strategies, reduce health care utilization, and improve long-term quality of life for patients with diabetes.

Study Limitations

This study is limited by its small sample size (n=30), which may have underpowered the detection of significant inter-group differences. Additionally, the short follow-up duration (six months) may not have been sufficient to capture the full impact of vascular and neurological changes. Objective measures such as nerve conduction studies, skin perfusion pressure, or transcutaneous oxygen tension could have provided more granular insights into microvascular and nerve function changes. Lastly, the homogeneity of the study population in terms of baseline sensory and vascular status may have limited the observed variability in outcomes.

Recommendations for Future Research

Future studies should consider larger, multicentric cohorts with stratification based on disease severity, duration of diabetes, and glycemic control. Incorporating additional interventions such as resistance or balance training, nutritional supplementation (e.g., alpha-lipoic acid or B vitamins), and structured foot care education may yield synergistic effects. Longer-term

follow-up is also warranted to assess whether modified Buerger's exercises confer sustained benefits or help delay the onset of more serious complications like foot ulcers or gangrene.

Conclusion

The study included 30 participants predominantly aged 50 years and above (53.3%) and mostly female (66.7%), equally distributed into two study groups (Group A and Group B). Over the 6-month period, no significant changes were observed in the Ankle-Brachial Pressure Index (ABPI), indicating stable peripheral arterial status in both groups. Sensory neuropathy, particularly small and large fiber neuropathy, was highly prevalent (76.7%) and remained consistent throughout the study duration.

Assessment of sensory modalities such as hot and cold sensation in both feet showed varying degrees of sensory loss, with mild and moderate loss more common than severe loss. These sensory impairments did not significantly differ between the two groups at any time point.

Statistical analysis revealed no significant association between the study groups and age, ABPI status, sensory nerve status, or sensory loss in hot and cold sensations across all evaluated time points.

Overall, the findings suggest that there was no significant improvement or deterioration in vascular status or sensory nerve function in either group over six months. Further studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods may be required to evaluate the potential effects of the interventions on foot perfusion and neuropathy in patients with diabetes.

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